

QUALITY MANAGEMENT GUIDANCE IN IMPROVING THE CHARACTER OF STUDENTS (CASE STUDY OF AN NASUHA PABEDILAN ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL AND AL ANWARIYAH TEGALGUBUG ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL, CIREBON REGENCY)

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Abstract

This problem is motivated by the lack of internalization of standardization of the quality of student guidance. The research procedure used is a qualitative approach with a case study design. *grand theory* in this study, namely the theory of quality from Deming and the theory of character from Lickona. The conclusion in this study explains that the quality management of mentoring has been realized in accordance with the principles of quality management theory, character theory and value systems so that an increase in the character of the santri is realized.

A. BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEM

Implementation of character education in Indonesia is still experiencing various problems. This problem shows that the application of character education in the world of education up to this point has not been able to show significant output, as what is meant by the goals of national education, namely developing abilities and forming dignified national character and civilization in the context of educating the nation's life, aiming at developing potential students to become human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become citizens of a democratic and responsible state. One of them was carried out at Islamic boarding schools. This problem is motivated by the low quality of character guidance at Islamic boarding schools,

Islamic boarding schools can in fact be developed more optimally for internal and external benefits, for this reason a role of management is needed as an approach that can develop and improve the quality of institutions universally and adapt to the conditions of the times. The coaching system is the key word for achieving the quality of Indonesian people who are intelligent, independent, have faith and are devoted to God Almighty as outlined in the National Education Goals. This pattern is expected to provide guarantees for Islamic

boarding schools to become strong and be able to meet the demands of society and world progress. In other words, pesantren are able to answer the challenges of the times.

Guidance for students and Islamic boarding schools as a whole can be carried out by involving various components of adequate instrumental input. It is hoped that the existence of a pondok caretaker who works effectively in a good guidance and management system under the auspices of Islamic leadership is expected to not only bring change to the popularity of the pondok, but lead to the formation of the personality of the santri, the character of the santri and the education that takes place therein.

B. RESEARCH QUESTION

Furthermore, the researcher details the focus of the problem which is the formulation of the research which is described in several research questions as follows:

1. How is Guidance Planning in Improving the Character of the Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
2. How is the Implementation of Guidance in Improving the Character of the Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
3. How is Guidance Evaluation in Improving the Character of Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
4. What is the follow-up to Guidance in Improving the Character of the Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
5. What are the obstacles to implementing Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
6. What is the solution to facing Guidance Barriers in Improving the Character of Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?
7. How is the Innovative Quality Management Model for Pondok Guidance implemented in Improving the Character of the Santri An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School in Cirebon Regency?

C. RESEARCH METHODS

Research on quality management of guidance in improving the character of students at An Nasuha Pabedilan Islamic Boarding School and Al Anwariyah Tegalgubug Islamic Boarding School, Cirebon Regency, uses a qualitative research approach. The reason for choosing a qualitative method is because the purpose of this study tends to explain

the description of education management in Islamic boarding schools. This is of course less meaningful when approached with quantitative research which places more emphasis on proving hypotheses by describing phenomena through numbers and statistics.

D. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research result

a. Guidance Planning in Improving the Character of Santri in Islamic Boarding Schools

Character coaching planning is in accordance with the principles of quality management which includes the vision, mission, goals, programs and character coaching materials. This research shows a positive direction from an Islamic educational institution that is oriented towards government policies towards character building.

b. Implementation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

The implementation of character guidance has been carried out quite well. This can be seen from all stages of implementation that have been carried out systematically, starting from (1) Instilling and Understanding Religious Values, (2) Instilling and Understanding National Values, (3) Instilling and Understanding Religious Moderation, (4) Instilling and Understanding Religious Moderation Understanding of Family Values, (5) Inculcating and Understanding Togetherness Values, (6) Inculcating and Understanding Independence Values, (7) Inculcating and Understanding Exemplary Values.

The implementation of the guidance has shown towards achieving the vision and mission of the Islamic Boarding School itself, this condition can be seen from the alignment of the vision, mission and objectives in guiding the character of the students.

c. Evaluation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

Evaluation of guidance in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools is good, it can be seen from the form of evaluation consisting of evaluation of knowledge, evaluation of attitudes and evaluation of skills in accordance with Permendikbud No. 4 of 2018 concerning Assessment of Student Learning Outcomes by Education Units.

d. Follow-up Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

The process of follow-up guidance in improving the character of the students is quite optimal, because of the communication made by the pesantren with the alumni. The role of the alumni of this pesantren can be as a motivator for their younger siblings and can also provide technical guidance to juniors in carrying out student activities at Islamic boarding schools, because these alumni have experience in activities at Islamic boarding

schools. Therefore they are willing to share their knowledge with their younger siblings who are doing extracurricular activities at the pesantren.

e. Barriers to the Implementation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

Barriers to the implementation of guidance in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools are generally not optimal, including:

- 1) Low knowledge of the pesantren management system
- 2) Maintenance of facilities and infrastructure that has not been maximized
- 3) There is still a lack of funds for mentoring programs

f. Solutions for Overcoming Guidance Obstacles in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

The solutions to the problems encountered in character coaching obstacles are quite effective, namely:

- 1) Conduct training related to the management of Islamic boarding schools
- 2) Recruiting one person to focus on maintaining infrastructure
- 3) Raising funds by opening a business as a form of pesantren independence.

g. Innovative Idea of Guidance Quality Management in Improving the Character of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools

The innovative idea of guiding quality management in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools is to combine grand theory with a value system in the implementation process. The grand theory in this research is Deming's theory of quality and Lickona's theory of character.

2. Discussion

a. Guidance Planning in Improving the Character of Santri

Planning for the quality of guidance in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools starts from the vision and mission that lead to guiding the character of students. Namely implementing the realization of quality human resources, efficient and persistent in maintaining the values of faith in Allah SWT, in all aspects of life and life, so that this pesantren focuses on the quality of graduates who focus on character guidance.

This is in line with Deming's theory of quality management. The definition of quality is very diverse and raised from different perspectives but has the same essence. Among them, as stated by Edwards Deming that quality is "a predictive degree of uniformity and dependability at a low cost, suited to the market"(W. Edwards Deming, 2006). Deming then defines quality according to context, customer perceptions, and customer needs and wants.

b. Implementation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri

Pesantren is a holistic integrative educational institution. The internalization of character education in Islamic boarding schools is emphasized to instill habits (habituation) about good things so that students become aware (cognitive) about what is right and wrong, are able to feel (affective) good values and are used to doing them (psychomotor).

The implementation of character guidance in Islamic boarding schools is divided into several steps, the first is planting and understanding the cultivation of religious values. This planting at Islamic boarding schools has been carried out since the beginning, when students entered the Islamic boarding school. Instilling religious values is done through learning classic books, cottage culture, regular cottage activities and extracurricular activities.

This is in line with Thomas Lickona who explained that character education is an effort that involves three aspects of intelligence, namely cognitive through moral knowing, affective through moral feeling, and psychomotor through moral acting. (Thomas Lickona, 1991).

c. Evaluation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri

Evaluations in the Islamic boarding school education system that are held generally follow those of other institutions that have just implemented some low-level cognitive aspects, such as knowledge, understanding and little application. While the level of analysis, synthesis and evaluation is rarely applied. For example, students develop their competence regarding the ability to paint cube nets. However, to be able to paint cube nets, at least knowledge (cognitive) is needed about the forms of cube nets and ways to draw perpendicular lines. This is in line with what was explained by Mahmudin (2016) that quality education can be identified from the aspects of student achievements, the learning process, the competency of graduates in applying and manifesting their potential in the midst of people's lives through critical thinking and problem solving skills.

d. Follow-up Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri

Follow-up guidance in the communication of the character of students is carried out by having communication at Islamic boarding schools which is very high, because students live in the same dormitory environment. Different cultural backgrounds, there must be ambiguity in communicating. With this, the students will become familiar with the pesantren culture that has been applied since their first entry. With this new habit, students become a culture. However, when alumni come to the outside world or a new environment, most of them come from non-Islamic boarding schools. The importance of communication must be built internally in educational institutions and also externally in educational institutions in the form of the community as an effort to build institutional synergy with the community.

The important thing that Deming explained about quality, especially in the first aspect of communication, there are two communication patterns in quality marketing. (1) communication with students, including academic and non-academic fields. (2) communication with madrasah stakeholders. Second, the elements that affect

communication are (1) madrasa achievements (2) madrasa characteristics. Third, the description of the effectiveness of the communication strategy in marketing the quality of education, namely, (1) the increasing number of students. (2) good communication with the community. (3) student achievement. Fourth, the obstacles in the quality marketing communication strategy, (1) funding, (2) teamwork, (3) geography.

e. Obstacles to the implementation of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri

Obstacles to the implementation of guidance in improving the character of students are generally still low in human resources at Islamic boarding schools

Islamic boarding schools in reality as a sub-culture are educational and social institutions, embodying a natural process of development of the national education system. change to the culture of a dynamic society.

Islamic boarding schools in many respects have similarities with traditional Islamic educational institutions in the Islamic world in the pesantren scientific tradition. Thus, basically Islamic boarding schools cannot be separated from social life in their participation in building the nation and state.

f. The solution to facing the Barriers to the Quality of Guidance in Improving the Character of Santri

In order to prepare reliable and professional human resources for students, it is necessary to conduct training related to the management of Islamic boarding schools. This training refers to the provision of theoretical provisions in the form of knowledge and abilities, which are appointed by the pesantren.

The real benefits that can be obtained from training in Islamic boarding schools are: (a) Increasing the quantity and quality of productivity, (b) Reducing the learning time required for employees to achieve accepted standards, (c) Creating an attitude of loyalty and more profitable cooperation, (d) Meet the needs of human resource planning, (e) Reduce the number and cost of work accidents, (f) Assist employees in their personal improvement and development.

g. Innovative Idea of Guidance Quality Management in Improving the Character of Santri

The innovative idea of guiding quality management in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools is to combine grand theory with a value system in the implementation process. The grand theory in this research is Deming's theory of quality and Lickona's theory of character.

This is in line with Deming's quality management theory which prioritizes each institution to carry out training so that the institution can have quality.

E. CONCLUSION

1. Character coaching planning is in accordance with the principles of quality management which includes the vision, mission, goals, programs and character coaching materials.
2. The implementation of the guidance has shown towards achieving the vision and mission of the Islamic Boarding School itself, this condition can be seen from the alignment of the vision, mission and objectives in guiding the character of the students.
3. Evaluation of guidance in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools is good, it can be seen from the form of evaluation consisting of evaluation of knowledge, evaluation of attitudes and evaluation of skills
4. The process of follow-up guidance in improving the character of the students is quite optimal, because of the communication made by the pesantren with the alumni.
5. Obstacles to the implementation of guidance in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools are generally not optimal knowledge of the pesantren management system
6. The solutions to the problems encountered in character coaching obstacles have been quite effective, namely: Conducting training related to the management of Islamic boarding schools
7. The innovative idea of guiding quality management in improving the character of students at Islamic boarding schools is to combine grand theory with a value system in the implementation process

Reference

- 1) Mahmudin, HI (2018). Integrated Quality Management in Islamic Education Perspective. National Seminar. 143–152.
- 2) Thomas, Lickona. (1991). Educating for Character: How Our Schools Can Teach Respect and Responsibility. In New York: Bantam Books, (p. 119).
- 3) W. Edwards Deming. (2006). Out Of The Crisis. MIT
- 4) Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System
- 5) Law Number 18 of 2019 concerning Islamic Boarding Schools
- 6) Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education
- 7) Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 concerning Implementation of PPK
- 8) Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 31 of 2020 concerning Islamic Boarding School Education